

THE EVALUATION OF ETHNICITY IN THE 2015 ELECTIONS IN NIGERIA

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Abstract

This paper examines the effect of ethnicity in the 2015 elections in Nigeria. The phenomenon of ethnicity has taken an alarming dimension in Nigeria, such that elections had become ethnically oriented. Also, ethnicity has been elevated to dominate national discourse, controls how people think and talk and determines what they support or oppose. Therefore, the electorates were thus ethnically conscious during the 2015 electoral period in Nigeria. For instance, ethnicity became so pronounced in the core North- West, North-Central, North-East Geo- Political zones of Nigeria mostly by the Hausa/Fulani which was the stronghold of General Muhammadu Buhari (Rtd) of the All Peoples Progressive Party (APC) where the electorates vote cast turned-out was 92.8% to his favour. While, in the South South Geo-political Zone most of the electorates voted massively for former President Good Ebele Jonathan of the People's Democratic Party (PDP). In addition, the South-East Geo-political Zone was not left out for ethnic party system. For instance, the All-Progressive Grand Alliance Party (APGA) that was

rooted among the Ibos, was massively voted for by the Ibos. This paper examines the nature of ethnicity, how it has affected the electorates and elections, and how to manage consequence ones in view of concretizing oneness, though our tribes may differ. The paper which was based on secondary sources of data about the voting pattern. reveals that majority of the Hausa/Fulani of the ethnic origins that lives in South- East, South-West and South-South Geo-Political Zones in Nigeria travelled home to cast their votes in support of General Muhammadu Buhari who they called "Sai Baba, " "Sai Buhari" which means "their own ". However, the paper concludes by taking recommendations to Nigerians, if unity and oneness in the country is envisaged.

Keywords: Ethnicity, Elections, Nigeria.

Introduction

Election is generally accepted in all climes of the world as the hallmarks of democracy. However, since the advent of democratization in Africa in the 1990's a great deal of emphasis has been placed on holding regular elections (Malomo, 2006:23). Elections are not a day activity, rather they are complex set of activities with different variables that act and feed on one another. In representative democracy, it is regarded as the only acceptable means of their enthroning new leadership or removing an existing one (Alao, Alao, Nwogwugwu, 2013).

Nigeria, a multi-ethnic nation-state with socio-cultural differences between its component ethnic groups all of which have resulted into cultural dissimilarity, aunts for twenty percent of the population of Africa, making one of every five Africans, a Nigerian. Located on the West Coast of Africa, the Federal Republic of Nigeria is the ninth most populous nation in the world with a population of over 170 million people (Adelegan, 2009).

Nigeria since inception, ethnicity has been elevated to dominate national discourse, controls how people think and talk and determines what they support or oppose. Ethnicity is promoted by the political elites, embraced by the young and the old, passed from generation to generations and even has base in the Constitution (Adeyanju, 2011). Electorates are thus ethnic conscious during electoral periods. This in-turn impede national government and promote inability to fight corruption, favouritism in employment, politics of divisions, distrust, mediocrity and suppression of justice and many others. Ethnicity has been adjudged as a leading factor in the process of choosing leaders at the national level.

The administrative division of Nigeria by Sir Arthur Richard former Governor-General of Nigeria in 1946 along ethnic lines greatly engineered ethnic consciousness of electorates in the nation-state called Nigeria. This in turn affected the voting pattern of electorates in a bid for an indigenus person to control the national government in the 1959 general election till the more recent 2015 general election where the election results vividly show ethnic

sentiments; electorates in turn voted ethnicity and not the candidate personality and even antecedents. Though cultural and ethnic diversity sometimes gives Nigeria energy and dynamism, it remains the greatest obstacles to the survival of Nigeria nation more than corruption. The Niger Area may have joined Nigeria, but it is fractured by ethnic distrust and disrespect (Okonkwo, 2015). The objectives of this study are to determine whether ethnic sentiment played a major role in the 2015 General elections; ascertain the extent which political elite encourage ethnic sentiment of the electorates for their personal interest in the 2015 general election in Nigeria; and examine if the level of the effect of ethnicity on elections brought about national disintegration and disunity.

Literature Review

The perception of ethnicity by social scientists has been one of the most popular subjects of study. A liberal scholar Mair, who is an anthropologist sees an ethnic groups as a people sharing the same historical experience, having the same culture, speaking the same language and sharing the belief about the future together (Mair, 1962).

The contention about ethnicity seems to have been empowered by high visibility of mobilized and politicized ethnic groups in multi-ethnic States of Africa and Asian countries with cultural pluralism. Van Evra (cited in Hale, 2004), asserted that ethnic groups are formed and once formed they tend to strongly endure. Hence the debate, whether ethnicity is a natural order of things or a social construct? According to Salawu and Hassan (2011), posited that ethnic groups as an informal interest group whose members are distinct from other members of other ethnic groups within the larger society because they share kingship, religious and linguistics ties.

Ugbana Okpu (1977), considered ethnicity from its evolutionary perspective. Ethnic groups according to him may be as a result of fusion of tribes or may come that, ethnicity thus seems to structure such actions by providing people with social radar that they use to efficiently identify or impose social possibilities and political constraints in a world of immense uncertainty and complexity.

The term ethnicity indicates that groups and identities have different mutual contacts. The implication of this is that groups do not live in isolation. What brings about variation in voting pattern of diverse ethnic groups is the nature of their socio- political and economic interactions. Ethnicity is considered as a phenomenon that mediates between diverse human relations and between different values and norms expressed and utilized differently at both the individual and collective levels and can influence the life processes of ethnic groups either positively or negatively (Seol, 2008). Perhaps, this is the reason why ethnicity has been considered as an aspect of the social relationship between the agents (social, political and

economic) who see themselves as being traditionally unique in (culture, language and belief etc) and different from members of other ethnic groups with whom they have regular socio-political relations. This informs us about why ethnicity has been described as frame within which certain socio-political and economic differences are conducted. Participation in electoral process in an ethnic diverse country like Nigeria can at the end of the day reproduce ethnic understanding and cooperation. For example, ethnicity can be mobilized in pursuit of perceived ethnic interest such as a demand for justice, equity in the distribution of socio-economic and political goods and equal representation in governance.

By implications ethnicity does not constitute any threat to socio-political and economic development of a State. It is the negative employment of ethnicity- negative attitudes towards those regarded as outsiders - that constitute the threat to socio-political development. Hence, the positive aspects of ethnicity often become insignificant in the multi-ethnic states. The interaction of ethnic group may either negatively or positively affect the socio-political and economic positions of another group. In essence, ethnicity becomes problematic when the various ethnic groups turn their table against one another in an attempt to have access to political power, thus degenerating from a form of political suppose into a basis of political conflict.

With a view of explaining the phenomenon ethnicity, one question that readily comes to mind here is why ethnic group have maintained their identity and why ethnicity has become the basis of mobilization and manipulation particularly in multi-ethnic states. One reason that can be given is that ethnic groups were stronger because of their socio-political and economic needs and the demand for such has given room for ethnic mobilization and manipulation by the political elites.

Seol (2008) maintains that ethnic manifestation should be understood in the context of individual and collective socio-political experiences in given society. In essence, the highly visibility of ethnicity is a direct result of a cultured and socio-economic conditions in existence over the generation. By explaining the presence extent and context of a group's behavior, one can predict or have an insight into what an ethnic group is up to. The prediction by scholars that ethnicity and ethnic attachment will lose their significance in the process of industrialization and civilization (Seol, 2008) seems to have lost its position. This is because there has not been a shift from ethnic attachment. What this means is that ethnic group today are affirming themselves more and more which has made ethnicity more significant because of the instrumental use of the phenomenon by political class.

The political class refers to a relatively smaller group of people that is aware and active in politics and from whom the national leadership is drawn. However, this class in Nigeria has, in a sense cultivated alliances whose primary interest is their socio-political gains through the

manipulation of ethnicity. Thus, ethnicity can be seen as process by which an appeal is made of the socio-political and economic differences in the ethnic groups through which the groups are manipulated. It is a psychological process that political elites manipulate for their own political interest, making the people ethnic conscious.

From the above, ethnicity can be viewed as social organization. King (2002), posits that ethnic identity may be narrowed or broadened in boundary terms and in relation to a specific socio-political and economic needs of the group; hence, the assertion that ethnicity refers both to aspect of gain and loss in interaction. According to Ericksen, (1993), this implies that ethnicity has both a political and organizational aspect, making it a significant phenomenon in societies where it is politically mobilized and manipulated. Calhoun (1993), comments that ethnicity was described as the product of manipulation or at least a recurrent innovation. It is a creation of political leaders who often utilize and depends on the strength of people's ethnic differences to gain socio-political advantages for their groups as well as pursuing their socio-economic well-being. Ethnic mobilization is made possible as result of group's competition for scarce socio-political and economic resources engendered by the process of modernization.

Ethnicity has also been defined as a social-construct. The meaning of this is that ethnicity is considered by-product of uneven to socio-economic resources orchestrated by the re-organization of the hitherto autonomous pre-colonial societies into artificial state structure, hence the explanation of ethnicity in relation to "external stimuli" (King, 2002). The result of this is the state of political instability in post-colonial Nigeria. This instability is made possible as a result of shifts in ethnicity after independence. In essence, the ethnic groups which had prior to colonialism maintained a critical relationship develop a new identity in which ethnicity was central and national, interest secondary.

In a shift from the above school of thought, Duran (cited in Seol, 2008) observes that in modern society, ethnicity may be regarded as rational group response to socio-political pressure and a basis for concerted group action. This is clearly and significantly demonstrated in contemporary African States. What one can deduct from this assertion is that ethnicity is a function of the structure of the socio-political and economic situation of the society. Thus, ethnicity can best be understood, as a deliberate strategic choice by groups and individuals as a means of obtaining socio political and economic status or rights. This points to the fact that ethnicity may not be regarded as acquired by belonging to particular ethnic group which shares the same origin but should be seen as a means of expression in specific socio-political and economic' spheres. Ethnicity is a tactics which groups or individual believe could propel and earn them their desired socio-political status hence its political utilization.

One new dimension that has been added to the phenomenon is the interpretation that ethnicity can be a "chameleon strategy" (Pieterse, 1993). What this means is that the minds of

members of a particular ethnic group operate in such a way that they can choose to be members of their ethnic group which they want to or members of the larger community (the state) when they feel it is politically or economically profitable. This explain why ethnicity has been classified by Green (2006) as a mid-level identity representing a group, perhaps small enough to strong political development if otherwise mobilized and manipulated positively. Ethnicity thus is the product of competition for socio-political and economic resources. From the above conceptualization of ethnicity, one can conclude that ethnicity is more' or less a mediating reference point" (Seol, 2008) through which ethnic groups in multi- ethnics' states with diverse human relations and values as it is Nigeria promote their group interests. However, the extent of utilization of ethnicity may be different between individuals and groups in the expression and utility of ethnicity; because of variation and the perception of their socio-political d economic positions. For example, in South Africa, Kenya, Honduras, Nigeria, Jamaica, India etc where there are diverse ethnic groups, ethnicity may serve as a common mediating reference point which may likely affect their socio-political and economic relations.

The implication of the above is that each ethnic group may tend to emphasize their ethnic identity and utilize it more effectively for their own-socio political and economic interest. However, this mediating reference point may eventually become - 01 in the hand of different ethnic political leaders who capitalize on these socio- logical bonds and utilize it for their own political and material' advantages. Individual always act in a manner that maximizes their socio-political and economic benefits. They can decide to act in the interest of their group or otherwise depending on what benefits them most. This explains the relevance of national cohesion in a multi-ethnic society to prevent impediments to good governance.

Theoretical Framework

This study is anchored on the theory and persuasion of the group theory. This theory was adopted because of the strong view of scholar such as Bently (1908), who as of the strong opinion that the interactions of groups are the basis of political life and rejected statist abstractions. In his opinion, group activity determined legislation, administration and adjudication. He also wants further to opine that institution approach should not be used for political analysis as these institutions are static as against politics which is dynamic and full of activities. He argued that politics is a group affair and each group is competing against each other for power. He also added that the pattern of process involving mass of activities and not a collection of individuals. The group emerges from frequent interaction among its individual members which is directed by their share interest. The interest leads to the organization of the groups.

Bently group theory received blessing of scholars like David Truman, Robert Daniel,

Grant Me Connell, Earl, Lathans among others. They saw power as diffused among many interest groups competing against each other. The group theories tried to establish the group, rather than the individual or the society, as the basic unit in the study of politics. It is construed as a generalized idea about how the organized 'few' determine and influence the direction of government at the expense of others. Group theory is developed within the context of the pluralist paradigm of politics. Pluralism argues essentially that power in the western industrialization societies is widely distributed among different groups. It is a major premise of pluralism that any group can ensure its political preferences and wishes are adopted and reflected in governmental action with sufficient determination and deployment of appropriate resources (Dalton, 2002).

Group theory begins with the proposition that interaction and struggle among groups is the central fact of political life. According to this theory, individuals are important in politics only when they act as part of, or on behalf of group interest. Group theory affirms that it is faster and more effective for individuals to approach government and their agencies by means of coordinating themselves as groups. Earl Lathan described a society as a simple universe of groups which combine, break and form coalitions and castellation of power in a restless alternation. The adoption of this theory as basis for the examination of the multi-party system and political development in Nigeria is simply as a result of the interplay of forces and struggle for power among various ethnic groups in the Nigerian society, which resulted that shortly after independence, voters have been voting along ethnic lines thereby fanning the embers of sectionalism.

The adoption of the group theory is to examine how the intrigues among the various ethnic groups shaping their preferences in the 2015 Presidential election affect generally political activities and in particular development of Nigeria political and economic system. It is also important to stress that all political systems are endowed with plethora of groups including political, religious, economic and social groups. This undoubtedly suggests that there is stiff competition among groups in the control of States resources.

Ethnicity in the 2015 General Elections

The 2015 Nigerian general elections turned out to be as acrimonious, bitter and a hateful play of brinkmanship as that of the first republic. Ahead of the elections, ethno-regional and religious sentiments were stirred-up across the country, threatening the very survival of the Nigeria state itself. The incumbent president rallied around himself ethno-regional supports of his minority kinsmen and the larger Igbos. Dangerous provocative and unguided statements were released, which heightened the tension across the country. Some of the rehabilitated ex-warlords of the Niger-Delta threatened to 'burn up the country' and returned back to the creeks

to take up arms struggle' against the state, should their own son lose out of power. The incumbent presidents also sought supports from various ethno-regional groups like OPC, Afenifere, Egbe Igbimo Agba Yoruba, among others. The former president equally paid several visits to many Christian organizations across the country to mobilize faithful voters to 'identify with their Christian brother'. In all these presidential campaigns and mobilization, huge amount of money was alleged to have been used to induce voters' supports for his re-election. The 2015 general elections were seen as a golden opportunity for the Northerners to wrestle back power, which they felt had been unjustly, denied them after the untimely demise of late President 'Yar'adua, The South-south minority groups also rallied behind the incumbent resident to secure a second term in office for him.

The Yoruba of the South-West who felt marginalized under the incumbent resident were quick to rally behind the opposition party that adopted their own son the Vice-President candidate. Across the length and breadth of the country, ethno- religion sentiments flared up and the presidential candidates of the leading political parties were prevailed upon to sign an accord (Abuja Peace Accord), committing themselves to maintaining peace before, during and after the elections. The leading presidential aspirants periodically kept returning to their ethno-regional bases for support and solidarity. The ember of ethnic sentiments was fanned out with dangerous misguided provocative statements. A famous one was recorded in Lagos ere there paramount traditional ruler (Oba of Lagos) summoned the Ndigbo leaders to his palace and directed to 'vote for his anointed candidate' in the gubernatorial election or perish in the Lagos Lagoon.

The general perception ahead of the 2015 general election was that the incumbent president as going into the electoral battle in a deficit and, therefore, disadvantaged position with regards to national security, corruption perception and indecisiveness. The fact that the presidential election had to be postponed by one and month to enable the government confront the Boko Haram menace, the success it achieved, only helped to cement the perception and charges of weakness on national security, which the success of the military campaign did little to change. The damage had been done and it takes an awful long time for political wounds to heal. The 2015 general election was not just about opposition party strategizing for election victory, which would be legitimate but something much deeper than that. This is about geo-political ethnic power grab at the expense of another or others that are otherwise entitled to it by virtue of extant power sharing tradition instituted by the PDP in the zoning of the Nigerian South. By this arrangement, Jonathan or another Southerner would be entitled to another four years in office, adopted as a necessary adjunct to the nation's democratic tradition. However, this arrangement had already been compromised by the denial of the northerners' opportunity to complete the unfinished terms of late president Yar'adua presidency.

Nigeria's political history would readily attest to the fact that the Yoruba ethnic group in the South-Western geo-political region or zone in Nigeria had always shunned the mainstream of Nigerian politics preferring instead to cling tenaciously to ethnic politicking and luxuriate in the comfort zone of its exclusive ethnic enclave in the Western region. Their aversion towards participation in Nigeria's mainstream politics and therefore fixation on regionalism is in indeed legendary and to a large extent, definitive of the broader Nigerian political history. All efforts in both pre and post-independence Nigeria to lure and even coax the Yorubas into the mainstream at the centre was violently repelled by mainstream Yoruba political elites in each and every general elections right up to the 2007 presidential election. It's no secret that they have been fighting for regional autonomy rather than moving to the centre.

The 2015 general election can therefore be analyzed in geo-ethnic conspiracies and betrayals between the South/West and the core north executing a strategic alliance to disrupt and upend the nation's political calculus. And this was helped in no small way by historical ethnic cleavages between the Igbos and the Yorubas, making it a whole lot easier for the Yorubas to turn their backs on the Igbos. The reported outburst of the Oba of Lagos threatening Ibos in Lagos to vote APC or else jump in the Lagos Lagoon and perish lends credibility to this conspiracy theory.

Result of the 2015 Presidential Election for the Two Leading Political Parties (All Progressive Congress (APC) and People Democratic Party (PDP))

Table I: Ethnic voting in the 2015 Presidential Election

State	APC	PDP	Variance
Abia	13,394	368,303	354,909
Adamawa	374,701	251,664	123,037
Akwa-Ibom	58,411	953,304	894,893
Anambra	17,926	660,762	642,836
Bauchi	931,598	86,085	845,513
Bayelsa	5,194	361,209	356,015
Benue	373,961	303,737	70,224
Bornu	473,543	25,640	447,903
Cross River	28,358	414,863	386,505
Delta	48,910	1,211,405	1,162,495
Ebonvi	19,518	373,653	354,135
Edo	208,469	286,869	78,400
Ekiti	120,331	176,466	56,135
Enugu	14,157	553,003	538,846
Gombe	361,245	96,873	264,372
Imo	133,245	96,873	36,372
Jigawa	885,998	142,904	743,094
Kaduna	1,127,760	484,085	643,675

Kano	1,903,999	215,779	1,688,220
Katsina	1,345,441	98,937	1,246,504
Kebbi	567,883	100,972	466,911
Kogi	264,451	149,987	114,464
Kwara	302,145	132,502	169,643
Lagos	792,460	632,327	160,133
Nasarawa	236,838	273,460	36,622
Niger	657,678	273,460	384,218
Ozun	308,290	149,222	159,068
Ondo	298,889	207,950	90,939
Osun	383,603	251,368	132,235
Oyo	528,620	249,929	278,691
Plateau	429,140	303,376	125,764
Rivers	69,238	1,487,075	1,417,837
Sokoto	671,926	152,199	519,727
Taraba	261,326	310,800	49,474
Yo be	446,265	25,526	420,739
Zamfara	612,202	144,833	467,369
FCT	146,399	157,195	10,796

Source: INEC Website,(www.inecnigeria.org)2015

From the above statistics, the All Progressive Congress (APC) defeated the People Democratic Party (PDP) with three million, two hundred and fifty eight thousand, nine hundred and seventeen (3,258,917) votes. The figure also clearly shows that ethnicity and bias played out in most of the northern states voting pattern in Nigeria, given credence to the emergence of a northerner, in the person of President Muhammadu Buhari of the All Progressive Congress (APC). It is observed that in Adamawa, Bauchi, Bornu, Gombe, Jigawa, Kaduna, Kano, Katsina, Kebbi, Yobe and Zamfara States, voting was tilted to one side in favour of the APC with a difference of 7,357,337 (seven million three hundred and fifty-seven thousand, three hundred and thirty seven) from the PDP. While the PDP whose Presidential candidate was from the Ijaw speaking area of the South, won in Southern and Eastern States like Rivers, Delta, and Akwa-Ibom states.

The Impact of Ethnicity on National Development

The question of whether Nigeria is underdeveloped as a result of ethnicity is not disputed through our findings so far. The facts are there for everyone to see. At present, however, the country is cogitating and nursing the idea of becoming one of the 20 largest economies of the world by the year 2020. This is a wishful thinking, an idea that is ill conceived, a wild goose chase. According to the July 2014 World bank calculation, the following countries are the 20 largest

economies:" United States, China, Japan, Germany, France, United Kingdom, Brazil, Italy, India, Canada, Russian Federation, Spain, Mexico, Korea, Australia, Netherlands, Turkey, Indonesia, Switzerland and Poland" (World Bank: 2014) which of these is Nigeria preparing herself to replace? The country has first to put her house in order before embarking on the ambitious program of becoming one of the 20 largest economies of the world by 2020. How can this dream be realized when foreign investments into the country is dwindling fast?

According to Charles Soludo, (a former CBN Governor) the UNCTAD "Foreign Direct Investment" (FDI) into Nigeria dropped by 62% in 2010 (from \$6million in 2009 to \$2.3 billion in 2010). The worst in many years and even worse than during the global crisis. While developing and transition economies increased their FDI inflows by 10% in 2010, Nigeria's FDI fell by whopping 62%" (Soludo: 2011) the investors are scared away by unfriendly and unstable business environment. Nigeria has a basic problem to contend with. This is one of the problems of ethnicity. Ethnicity is an albatross, a cog in the wheel of progress. This problem ought to be solved in order for the country to join the comity of progressive nations.

The level of ethnic rivalry in Nigeria 'has made it impossible for her to produce the right crop of leaders who live above boards, who exude impeccable and predictable character and who are ready to spend themselves for the development of the nation. Ethnic affiliation has not allowed such leaders to emerge. As' each election, the emphasis has always being on where the candidate came from rather than on the right candidate for the election. This explains why the national assembly is replete with many people who are there neither for the interest of the nation nor for their own ethnic groups. They short themselves up into the national assembly by weeping-up ethnic sentiment. They describe themselves as best candidate to fight for the right of their respective ethnic groups. The suitability of their character was hardly called to question as soon as they were elected they went into self-service.

The lid of this self-service was thrown up in 20 10 by the then Governor of the Central Bank Mr Sanusi Lamido during his convocation lecture at Igbinedion University, Okada. According to him, "25% of the over-head of the federal government go to the national assembly". His revelation opened the facts about the ills in the society. He stood his ground, however, as the members of the national assembly at that time tried a cow him down with the aim of making him reconsider his claim. But before Sanusi's historic lecture, Itse Sagay had reported that the annual salary and allowance of a Nigerian senator stood at N240m (Iredia, 2010). This jumbo pay was

possible because the electorate did not elect people with conscience and credible character. Even when these revelations from the jumbo pay were made public no attempt was made by any ethnic group to recall their members, If one convert that jumbo pay of N240m into dollars at the conservative exchange rate of N150 per dollar, it means that the Nigerian senator was taking home annually \$1.6m dollars as salaries and allowances at least at the time that Itse Sagay made his report. This amount is bigger than the annual salary of the American president, Vice-President, the majority leader in the senate, the speaker of the House of Representatives and the majority leader of the House of Representatives all put together. The annual salaries of these American officials are as follows: the President - \$400,000, Vice-President -\$230,700, Senate Majority Leader - \$193,400, Senate Minority Leader-\$193,400, Speaker of House of Representative - \$193,400.

Another effect of ethnicity which will continue to hamstring the development of the country unless the problem of ethnicity is properly addressed is the issue of federal character. This is an attempt made to pacify ethnic group. The federal character arrangement is enshrined in the constitution. The reason behind it may appear plausible. It is to ensure greater unity of the country. But the underlying politics that gave rise to it breeds mediocre in the running of government. The members of the constituent assembly for the 1989 Constitution wanted to include merit on the existing federal character arrangement. What some members wanted to add to the federal character clause in the constitution: "nothing in this sub-section shall preclude the employment of merit and excellence and federal character means as much as practical representation of all states of the federation" (Aniagolu: 1993). This was put to vote. It was defeated by 81 to 186. The ethnic groups that were lagging behind educationally canvassed for its defeat. There was the fear that the question of merit would put them in disadvantage position in the federal character clause.

Since merit has been rejected as a criterion for serving the nation all manner of people has been appointed to hold public offices in which they had neither the training nor the experience. How can the nation progress when those who drive her economy are not qualified to do so? This is a tragic situation. The ministries, parastatals and government agencies are now filled with incompetent officials. And since their entry into these offices was not based on merit, they do not make any positive impact in their various *Nemo dat quo non habet*. They spend their time on what they know how to do best, namely to defraud the nation.

Ethnic rivalry shows it hydra in Presidential elections: it leads to the emergence of

incompetent presidents. To defuse ethnic tension some have adopted the rotational idea of the presidency among the six geo-political zones. But then the implication of this is the same as that of federal character clause. The implication is that the president is elected not on basis of merit but rather on the basis of where he comes from. The zoning of the presidency, though it is not a constitutional matter is threatening the corporate existence of the country. The altercations and noises from different ethnic groups are distraction in the running of government. in the 2011 Presidential election, there was loss of lives and properties in the northern part of the country as a result of agitation against the outcome of the election.

Ethnicity has flourished because the Nigerian elites who inherited the colonial state have conceptualized development as transferring resources from civil public to primordial public. It is in this view that Cletus Umezina argued that Nigeria is a failed State, backing his opinion up with a number of factors that included cultural and value decadence, fragile political structure, and poor leadership and frequent ethno-religious crisis (Umezina, 2010). Conflicts in Nigeria most often link with religion or ethnicity, and mostly deployed to settle economic and political imbalances; breeding the evolution of ethnic militias such as the Bakkasi Boys; Movement for Actualization of Sovereign State of Biafra (MASSOB); Odua People's Congress (OPC), Egbesu Boys; Movement for Emancipation of Niger Delta (MEND); Arewa Forum; Yandaba; Boko Haram and Ombatse Group etc.

Conclusion

From what has been discussed so far, it can be seen that as a nation, Nigeria, has failed to properly manage her political relations in a manner that is characteristic of the civilized societies of the world. Nigeria has performed poorly on the political plane as a result of which the country's economic performance has been predictably affected. All efforts should have been directed to establishing a sound economy for economic self-reliance had been unintelligently expended on political power struggle, political anarchy and political thuggery, all of which are compounded by the factors of ethnicism.

For institutionalization of lasting democracy in Nigeria, her ethnic plurality notwithstanding, the wrongs of ethnicism must be righted. This can best be done by good governance. The nation needs a purposeful leadership that has a vision of how to place its citizens at the centre of political project without recourse to ethnic chauvinism and see acquisition of

political power as not an end in itself but a means for serving the collective welfare of its people regardless of their ethnic origin. A leadership that recognizes and respects the people that, make up the nation; and treats all communities as its constituency, thereby allaying the fear of ethnic domination.

With the suggestions above, the Nigeria society will be able to reduce the incidence of ethnicism in the country's body polity. This will transform particular loyalties to loyalty to the nation. It will reduce the common syndrome of ethnic loyalty, which has always resulted into unhealthy political struggle and which has manifested in various types of protest and instabilities.

Recommendations

This paper recommends that:

1. There is need for government to re-educate or re-orientate the political elites on the constant danger of using the ethno-religious card to acquire electoral offices or leadership position.
2. The principle of Federal Character enshrined in the Constitution should be reviewed to enable it perform integrative function without compounding merit, and also, ensure social justice and equity is put into play.
3. Create more space for Nigerians to participate in the affairs of the country as well as, those of their various communities. This will go a long way in reducing alienation which oftentimes is a major promoter of ethnic nationalism.
4. Nigerians need to be well-enlightened about the values that make for peaceful co-existence.
5. Constitutional amendment is needed to adequately address clauses that abrogate powers to ethnic or regional structures. For example, the constitutional provision (Section 147, sub-section 3 of the 1999 Constitution) mandates the appointment of at least a minister per state. This has unleashed mini tribal wars in many states.
6. There is need for a fairer resources management formula that would be acceptable to those who pay the human and environmental prize for Nigeria's oil powered economy.
7. Nigeria must control corruption by making stealing impossible and prosecution swift and certain. Meanwhile the judiciary must wake-up to the 21st century justice system administration of criminal cases, particularly those that threaten national security, such as corruption; the country

must enthrone transparency and accountability in governance.

8. Nigeria needs cultural orientation on the beauty of diversity. Therefore, this study calls on Nigerians, the government, and the African communities to focus on addressing the human factors that are contributing to conflicts; underdevelopment and bad governance as against vilifying the beauty of the diversities.

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